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Title: INFLAMMATORY ACTIVATION AND LEFT VENTRICULAR MASS IN ESSENTIAL
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Corresponding Author: Dr. Miguel Rivera, MD

Corresponding Author's Institution: Hospital La Fe

First Author: Esther Roselló-Lletí

Order of Authors: Esther Roselló-Lletí; Miguel Rivera, MD; Luís Martínez-Dolz; Jose R González-Juanatey; Raquel Cortés; Alejandro Jordán; Pedro Morillas; Catheline Lauwers; Jose R Calabuig; Isabel Antorrena; Beatriz de Rivas; Manuel Portolés; Vicente Bertomeu

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Abstract: ABSTRACT

Objectives: Inflammation is an independent risk factor for high blood pressure, and as a consequence inflammatory cytokines could be related with LVH. We sought to assess the association and predictive role of different cytokine levels with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) in a group of patients with essential hypertension.

Methods: We studied 251 asymptomatic hypertensive patients (142 with LVH and 109 without LVH), referred from 11 hospitals. A routine physical examination, laboratory analyses and echo-Doppler

study were performed. Plasma soluble TNF receptors (sTNF-R1 and sTNF-R2), interleukin-6 (IL-6) and interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1ra) were centrally determined.

Results: Hypertensive patients with LVH had higher inflammatory cytokine levels than the group without hypertrophy ($p < 0.001$). Multivariate linear regression reported that sTNF-R1 ($p < 0.01$) was an independent predictor of left ventricular mass index. All cytokines had significant area under the curves for detection of LVH, but sTNF-R1 has the highest area, 0.71 ± 0.03 ($p < 0.001$). Finally, prevalence of LVH was increased in the group of patients with higher cytokine levels, and logistic regression analysis showed that sTNF-R1 (odds ratio=2.59, CI 95% of 1.14 - 5.87) was independent predictor of LVH.

Conclusions: Cytokine levels were significantly correlated with left ventricular mass index in hypertensive patients. The sTNF-R1 was independent predictor of left ventricular mass index. Plasma sTNF-R1 concentrations could be and predictive factor of LVH in patients with essential hypertension.

Suggested Reviewers:

Opposed Reviewers:

REPLY TO THE EDITOR'S COMMENTS

First of all, we would like to thank the Editor for his helpful comments.

Table 4

1. With regard to the CI for Gender in the Table 4, we agree with the Editor that it is mistaken. We have corrected this value in the **Table 4 [CI 95% (-6.692) – 2.421]**.
2. With regards to the potential collinearity between the different variables included in the multivariate regression analysis, we agree with Editor and an analysis of collinearity was performed. Different collinearity statistics as tolerance, variance inflation factor (VIF), condition index and variance proportions, were calculated.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% CI for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower	Upper	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	23,26	4,830		4,81	,000	13,747	32,777		
	Age	,438	,082	,348	5,36	,000	,277	,599	,697	1,436
	Gender	-4,517	1,930	-,132	-2,34	,020	-8,319	-,716	,918	1,090
	Log IL-1ra	,000	,006	,002	,03	,969	-,012	,012	,831	1,203
	Log IL-6	-,159	,424	-,022	-,37	,708	-,995	,677	,831	1,203
	Log TNF-R1	,016	,005	,271	3,47	,001	,007	,025	,482	2,074
	Log TNF-R2	-,001	,002	-,040	-,53	,594	-,006	,003	,516	1,939

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% CI for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower	Upper	Tolerance	VIF
2	(Constant)	24,123	19,385		1,24	,216	-14,26	62,507		
	Age	,039	,155	,031	,25	,799	-,267	,345	,232	4,315
	Gender	-2,136	2,301	-,062	-,92	,355	-6,692	2,421	,752	1,330
	Log IL-1ra	-,007	,007	-,078	-1,10	,271	-,020	,006	,688	1,453
	Log IL-6	-,384	,455	-,056	-,84	,401	-1,285	,517	,773	1,294
	Log TNF-R1	,015	,006	,228	2,40	,002	,003	,027	,378	2,642
	Log TNF-R2	-,001	,002	-,052	-,58	,562	-,006	,003	,423	2,362
	Known HT duration	,029	,012	,167	2,43	,016	,005	,052	,725	1,379
	SBP	,046	,052	,059	,88	,378	-,057	,150	,768	1,303
	BMI	1,685	,340	,416	4,96	,000	1,013	2,358	,482	2,073
	EF	,023	,197	,007	,11	,908	-,367	,412	,893	1,120
	Vp	-,470	,114	-,292	-4,11	,000	-,696	-,244	,672	1,488
	GFR	-,137	,068	-,254	-2,02	,045	-,272	-,003	,216	4,634
	ARA II	-,285	2,773	-,008	-,10	,918	-5,776	5,207	,511	1,955
	ECAI	-1,023	2,911	-,028	-,35	,726	-6,786	4,741	,536	1,866
	Diuretics	-3,713	2,170	-,109	-1,71	,090	-8,009	,584	,840	1,190
	Beta Blockers	2,689	2,560	,067	1,05	,296	-2,379	7,757	,833	1,201

According to *Kleinbaum et al (1988)*, variance inflation factors (VIF) values greater than 10 and tolerance values smaller than 0.10 may indicate the presence of multicollinearity. In our multivariate regression analysis, any of cytokines had these conditions in models 1 or 2 of table 4.

Kleinbaum DG, Kupper LL, Muller KE. Applied Regression Analysis and Other Multivariate Methods. PWS-KENT Publishing Company 1988).

Furthermore, according to *Belsley (1991)*, if Condition index > 30 and a variance proportion higher then 0.5 then there is strong collinearity between these variables. In our analysis, any of cytokines reached these conditions in models 1 or 2 of table 4.

Belsley DA. Conditioning Diagnostics: Collinearity and Weak Data in Regression. John Wiley & Sons. 1991).

Collinearity Diagnostics

Model	Dimension	Eigen value	Condition Index	Variance Proportions							
				Constant	Age	Gender	Log IL-1ra	Log IL-6	Log TNF-R1	Log TNF-R2	
1	1	5,592	1,000	,00	,00	,01	,01	,01	,00	,00	
	2	,550	3,188	,00	,00	,59	,06	,03	,01	,00	
	3	,312	4,233	,00	,00	,02	,02	,73	,05	,06	
	4	,274	4,521	,00	,00	,02	,70	,20	,06	,02	
	5	,167	5,791	,07	,06	,24	,14	,00	,09	,07	
	6	,086	8,046	,00	,00	,00	,01	,02	,72	,83	
	7	,019	17,344	,92	,93	,12	,06	,02	,06	,01	

Condition index was never > 30.

Collinearity Diagnostics

Model	Eigen value	Condition Index	Variance Proportions																
			Constant	Age	Gender	Lg IL-1ra	Lg IL-6	Lg TNF-R1	Lg TNF-R2	Known HT	SBP	BMI	EF	Vp	GF R	AR A II	EC AI	Diuretics	BB
1	12,17	1,000	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	
2	1,047	3,411	,00	,00	,01	,00	,01	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,10	,15	,00	,01
3	,830	3,831	,00	,00	,00	,01	,00	,00	,00	,07	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,57	
4	,708	4,146	,00	,00	,03	,06	,09	,01	,01	,02	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,09	,17	,02
5	,547	4,719	,00	,00	,18	,01	,00	,01	,01	,17	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,02	,03	,13	,08
6	,442	5,252	,00	,00	,00	,01	,02	,00	,01	,23	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,03	,03	,51	,07
7	,322	6,154	,00	,00	,18	,06	,53	,00	,00	,12	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,01	,01	,09	,09
8	,309	6,273	,00	,00	,31	,01	,18	,06	,08	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,02	,02	,02
9	,238	7,155	,00	,00	,09	,52	,02	,04	,03	,19	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,09	,04	,02	,00
10	,154	8,897	,00	,00	,00	,22	,04	,01	,00	,06	,00	,00	,00	,01	,00	,68	,62	,00	,08
11	,102	10,946	,00	,02	,02	,03	,01	,13	,50	,03	,00	,00	,00	,00	,05	,00	,00	,00	,00
12	,060	14,234	,00	,03	,02	,00	,00	,66	,20	,00	,01	,00	,00	,00	,09	,00	,00	,08	,04
13	,031	19,758	,00	,01	,01	,00	,05	,00	,01	,06	,04	,02	,00	,68	,07	,01	,02	,01	,01
14	,017	26,933	,00	,11	,04	,00	,01	,01	,00	,02	,47	,15	,02	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00	,00
15	,010	35,509	,01	,02	,03	,00	,01	,06	,13	,00	,35	,03	,44	,22	,01	,02	,01	,00	,00
16	,006	45,422	,01	,48	,06	,06	,01	,02	,02	,01	,06	,79	,05	,00	,59	,03	,01	,05	,00
17	,002	77,074	,98	,32	,01	,01	,01	,00	,00	,01	,06	,00	,49	,08	,18	,02	,00	,00	,00

When condition index is > 30 there is not simultaneously any cytokine with variance proportion higher than 0.5 (model 15, 16 or 17).

Thus, there is not multicollinearity between cytokine levels, and we think that it is not required another approach in our case.

Respecting to the SE's are bigger than the B for 3 cytokines involves that the CI would be large and would include the number 0, thus these variables do not reach statistical significance.

3. Finally, the 95% CI for the binary logistic data now appears in the Results section **(page 10, last paragraph)** and in the results section of abstract.

Once again, we would like to thank the Editor for his pertinent comments and suggestions that have really helped improve the manuscript.

REPLY TO COMMENTS OF REVIEWER #1

We thank Reviewer #1 for his helpful comments.

1. Referring to be more conservative and consider sTNF-R1 solely as an independent predictor of LVM and LVH, we agree with reviewer #1 and we accepted to be more conservative. We have considered sTNF-R1 solely as independent predictor of LVM and LVH, and included this phrase in abstract and conclusions section.
2. Respecting to the fact that the predictive performance of cytokines could not be compared to that from ECG, we have included it as one of the study limitations:

“Furthermore, another limitation is that the predictive performance of cytokine concentrations could not be compared to that obtained from conventional ECG, due to insufficient ECG data”. (page 13, line 19).

3. With regards to the 95% CI for the binary logistic data is now included in the results section of abstract, as reviewer #1 suggests.
4. With regards to change the word “diameter” for “thickness” in the table 1, we agree with reviewer #1 and we have changed it.
5. Finally, we have abbreviated “standard error” as SE, and we have included this abbreviation in the footnotes of the table 4, as reviewer #1 suggests.

Once again, we would like to thank Reviewer #1 for his pertinent comments and suggestions that have helped improve the manuscript.

REPLY TO COMMENTS OF REVIEWER #2

We thank Reviewer #1 for his helpful comments. In addition, we are aware that the measurement of troponin levels in chronic patients does not differentiate between ischemic and non-ischemic cardiomyopathy.

1. Respecting to the grammatical errors indicated by the reviewer # 2, we have changed them in the abstract and results section. Furthermore, we have rephrased the expression “**was independent predictor factor**” in the abstract and conclusions section for this sentence: “**was an independent predictor of**”.

Once again, we would like to thank the reviewer #2 for his pertinent comments and suggestions that have helped improve the manuscript.

Word count abstract: 220

Word count text: 2750

Number of references: 33

Number of figures and tables: 1 figure and 5 tables

INFLAMMATORY ACTIVATION AND LEFT VENTRICULAR MASS IN ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION

Running head: Inflammation and hypertrophy in hypertension.

Esther Roselló-Lletí^a, PhD; Miguel Rivera^a, MD, PhD; Luís Martínez-Dolz^b, MD; Jose R. González Juanatey^c, MD; Raquel Cortés^a, PhD; Alejandro Jordán^d, MD; Pedro Morillas^e, MD; Catheline Lauwers^f, MD; Jose R. Calabuig^g, MD; Isabel Antorrena^h, MD; Beatriz de Rivasⁱ, MD; Manuel Portolés^j, PhD; Vicente Bertomeu^e, MD, PhD.

^aCardiocirculatory Unit, Research Center, Hospital Universitario La Fe, Valencia, Spain; ^bCardiology Unit, Hospital Universitario La Fe, Valencia, Spain; ^cCardiology Unit, Hospital Clínico, Santiago de Compostela, Spain; ^dCardiology Unit, Hospital General Universitario, Elche, Spain; ^eCardiology Unit, Hospital Universitario San Juan, Alicante, Spain; ^fCardiology Unit, Hospital San Francesc de Borja, Gandía, Spain; ^gInternal Medicine, Hospital Universitario La Fe, Valencia, Spain; ^hCardiology Unit, Hospital Marina Baixa, Villajoyosa, Spain; ⁱAstraZeneca, Madrid, Spain; ^jCell Biology and Pathology Unit, Research Center, Hospital Universitario La Fe, Valencia, Spain.

Disclosure: The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Address for correspondence:

Dr. Miguel Rivera, MD, PhD, FACC, FESC

Cardiocirculatory Unit, Research Center,

Hospital Universitario La Fe

Avd. Campanar, 21

46009-Valencia, Spain

Tel: 34 96 386 27 97

Fax: 34 96 197 30 18

e-mail: rivera_jmi@gva.es

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Inflammation is an independent risk factor for high blood pressure, and as a consequence inflammatory cytokines could be related with LVH. We sought to assess the association and predictive role of different cytokine levels with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) in a group of patients with essential hypertension.

Methods: We studied 251 asymptomatic hypertensive patients (142 with LVH and 109 without LVH), referred from 11 hospitals. A routine physical examination, laboratory analyses and echo-Doppler study were performed. Plasma soluble TNF receptors (sTNF-R1 and sTNF-R2), interleukin-6 (IL-6) and interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1ra) were centrally determined.

Results: Hypertensive patients with LVH had higher inflammatory **cytokine levels** than the group without hypertrophy ($p < 0.001$). Multivariate linear regression reported that sTNF-R1 ($p < 0.01$) was an independent predictor of left ventricular mass index. All cytokines had significant area under the curves for detection of LVH, but sTNF-R1 has the highest area, 0.71 ± 0.03 ($p < 0.001$). Finally, prevalence of LVH was increased in the group of patients with higher cytokine levels, and logistic regression analysis showed that sTNF-R1 (odds ratio=2.59, *CI 95% of 1.14 – 5.87*) was independent predictor of LVH.

Conclusions: Cytokine levels were significantly correlated with left ventricular mass index in hypertensive patients. The sTNF-R1 **was independent predictor of** left ventricular mass index. Plasma sTNF-R1 concentrations could be and predictive factor of LVH in patients with essential hypertension.

Key words: inflammation, cytokines, interleukins, hypertrophy, essential hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is one of the most important risk factors for cardiovascular disease, but the molecular mechanisms by which elevated blood pressure leads to inflammation are uncertain. Experimental evidence suggests that hypertension (HT) may promote endothelial expression of cytokines¹. There is some evidence that an increase in pulse pressure stimulates inflammation, specifically pulse pressure is associated with activation of the TNF-alpha system². In addition, other cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) and interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1ra) are increased in HT^{3, 4}. Furthermore, published data suggest that chronic inflammation could be an independent risk factor for high arterial blood pressure⁵ and several studies have shown that inflammation is associated with an increased risk of acute cardiovascular mortality and cardiovascular events in healthy people^{6, 7}.

Then, the development of left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) in hypertensive patients has a negative prognostic impact and is associated with cardiovascular morbidity and mortality⁸. Increased plasma concentration of different biochemical markers, such as those of the natriuretic peptide family, is associated with increased wall stress. Furthermore, the relationship between high levels of these molecules and left ventricular mass index (LVMI) has been established in hypertensive patients⁹. However, previous studies on the relationship between LVH and inflammatory markers in essential HT are limited¹⁰.

We hypothesize that the presence of LVH in HT may be related with the activation of the immune system even in hypertensive patients under medical treatment, and therefore, cytokines can be markers of LVH. The aim of this study was to assess the association between inflammatory markers with blood pressure and LVH, and to

evaluate their diagnostic and predictive power of LVH in a group of patients with essential HT.

METHODS

Patients

Patients analyzed in this cross-sectional study met these inclusion criteria: a previous diagnosis of hypertension, as defined by the Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure¹¹. Furthermore, exclusion criteria were secondary HT, left ventricular ejection fraction <50, ischemic (medical history, echo-Doppler, troponin T assay) or dilated cardiomyopathy, permanent arrhythmia, more than mild valvular disease, chronic diseases, acute and chronic liver or renal diseases, immunological diseases, HIV, alcoholism and drug addiction.

After these exclusions, 251 Caucasian asymptomatic hypertensive patients (142 with LVH and 109 without LVH), from 11 participating hospitals, were studied. All patients underwent a routine physical examination, electrocardiogram, echo-Doppler study and laboratory analyses. Physicians using a standardized protocol measured systolic and diastolic blood pressure in the left arm of seated subjects between 08:00 and 11:00 AM, following the recommendations of The American Heart Association¹¹. All patients were on stable medical therapy for at least 2 months before study enrollment with angiotensin II receptor antagonist 50%, diuretics 44%, angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors 32%, beta blockers 21%, statins 26% and calcium-channel blockers 20%. Body mass index was calculated as the weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared, and obesity was defined as body mass index >30 kg/m². Glomerular filtration rate was calculated using the Cockcroft-Gault method¹². The

procedure was approved by the appropriate institutional review boards or ethics review committees of each study center, and the study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of good clinical practice and with ethical standards for human experimentation established by the Declaration of Helsinki. Every patient signed a written informed consent for their inclusion in the study.

Cytokine and cytokine receptor measurement

Venous blood was taken by venipuncture into pyrogen-free vacuum tubes containing EDTA, as anticoagulant, with the subjects in sitting position between 08:00 and 11:00 AM, centrifuged immediately and frozen at -80°C and only thawed once. Plasma concentrations of sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra were determined at a central laboratory by specific commercial sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (Hbt human sTNF-R1 ELISA test kit, Hycult Biotechnology, the Netherlands; Hbt human sTNF-R2 ELISA test kit, Hycult Biotechnology, the Netherlands; Strakine human IL-6 ELISA, Strathmann Biotec, Germany; and Quantikine human IL-1ra, R&D Systems, U.S.A.). The tests were quantified at 450 nm in a dual wavelength microplate reader (Sunrise, TECAN, Austria) using Magellan software (version 2.5 TECAN, Austria). The sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra tests have limits of detection of 25 pg/ml, 25 pg/ml, 0.3 pg/ml and 22 pg/ml, respectively. Our CV intra-assay and inter-assay were for sTNF-R1 (6.5% and 9.1%), for sTNF-R2 (4.7% and 7.6%), IL-6 (6.1% and 8.3%) and IL-1ra (4.9% and 5.4%, respectively).

Echo-Doppler study

The study was performed using standard hospital echocardiographic systems equipped with 2.5-4 MHz transducers found in regular clinical practice. The

echocardiographic examinations were performed using the standard apical and parasternal long axis views. Doppler echocardiogram images were stored on videotape and analyses of recordings were all performed in a central laboratory. Cardiologists assessing left ventricular function were blinded to the assay. M-mode and two-dimensional images, Doppler spectrum and color Doppler were analyzed off-line, using a computerized system (Eco-dat; Software Medicina SA). For each patient, four consecutive beats were measured and averaged for each Doppler variable.

To obtain left ventricular ejection fraction, the area-length method¹³ was used and calculated as $100 * [(telediastolic\ volume - telesystolic\ volume) / telediastolic\ volume]$. By pulsed Doppler, peak flow velocity in early diastole (E wave) and during atrial contraction (A wave) was measured at valve level, calculating the E/A ratio. Mitral flow propagation velocity (Vp) was determined using the previously described method¹⁴. Left ventricular mass was measured following the Devereux method¹⁵ and in our study, LVH was defined as LVMI $>46.7\ g/m^{2.7}$ in women and $>49.2\ g/m^{2.7}$ in men, when the LV mass was indexed for height¹⁶. Intra-observer variability was consecutively evaluated in series of 40 patients. Variability was expressed as the absolute difference divided by the mean value of echocardiographic measurements, for left ventricular mass variability being $8.4 \pm 6\ %$.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation or median and interquartile range (inflammatory marker values) and categorical variables as percentage. Results for each variable were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov Smirnov method. Comparison of data between groups of patients with normal distribution was carried out with unpaired Student t test. Cytokine and cytokine receptor

levels showed no normal distribution, they were compared using the Mann-Whitney test, and correlations were performed using Spearman's rank coefficient.

Furthermore, multivariate linear regression analysis was performed using LVMI as dependent variable. Model 1 was applied to evaluate the relationship of sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra with LVMI after adjusting for age and gender. This Model was then repeated with additional variables that could influence hypertrophy, such as known HT duration, blood pressure, GFR, body mass index, EF, Vp and treatment. Cytokine levels were log-transformed before multivariate linear regression was performed. The discrimination of the best model was based on the principle of least mean square and higher R-square.

The relativity, sensitivity, specificity and predictive value of plasma cytokine levels for the presence of LVH were assessed by construction of receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves. In addition, prevalence of LVH, according to optimal cut-off cytokine values from ROC curves, was compared using Fisher's exact test.

Finally, to determine whether studied inflammatory markers were independent predictors for LVH (cut-off values were selected from the ROC curve), binary logistic regression analyses were performed with all relevant variables included in the models. An incremental approach was used for continuous variables (calculated odds ratios are related to the increase in a certain continuous variable by a given amount), and dichotomous risk factors were coded with an indicator variable of 1 for having the condition and 0 for its absence.

All statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 10.1) software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois). A p value lower than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of our hypertensive patients with (n=142) and without (n=109) LVH. As expected, patients with LVH were significantly older ($p<0.001$), had significantly higher systolic blood pressure ($p<0.05$), pulse pressure ($p<0.0001$), body mass index ($p<0.001$) and lower glomerular filtration rate ($p<0.001$) compared to non-hypertrophic patients, and the diastolic left ventricular function parameters diminished (E/A, $p<0.001$; Vp, $p<0.001$). Plasma sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra levels were increased in LVH hypertensive patients compared to non-LVH group, as shown in Table 2.

Plasma concentrations of cytokines and cytokine receptors were significantly correlated with age, systolic blood pressure, pulse pressure, LVMI, glomerular filtration rate, body mass index, waist circumference and left ventricular function parameters (EF and Vp), except plasma IL-1ra that was related only with age, pulse pressure and body mass index (Table 3). Then, a multivariate linear regression analysis was used to test the independent predictive power of cytokines (sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra), age, gender, known HT duration, systolic blood pressure, glomerular filtration rate, body mass index, ejection fraction, Vp and treatment on LVMI in this group of hypertensive patients. The best model included sTNF-R1 ($p<0.01$), known HT duration ($p<0.05$), body mass index ($p<0.001$), Vp ($p<0.001$) and glomerular filtration rate ($p<0.05$) as independent factors, accounting for an r^2 of 0.60 ($p<0.001$) (Table 4).

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were performed to analyze the capability of sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra for detecting LVH in our hypertensive patients. All cytokine concentrations obtained a significant area under the curve (AUC); plasma sTNF-R1 had the highest AUC, 0.71 ± 0.03 (95% CI, 0.65 – 0.78;

p<0.001). Optimal cut-off values, sensitivities, specificities and predictive values for each cytokine are shown in Table 5.

Furthermore, we investigated the prevalence of hypertrophy in our patients according to the cut-off values selected from the ROC curves (Figure 1). Plasma sTNF-R1 concentration above 354 pg/mL had a higher number of LVH patients compared to the lower concentrations (71% vs. 38%; p<0.001). Increased sTNF-R2 levels (above 700 pg/mL) also showed higher prevalence of LVH (63% vs. 45%; p<0.01). Plasma IL-6 above 2.02 pg/mL and IL-1ra above 175 pg/mL also had a higher percentage of hypertrophic patients (67% vs. 42%, p<0.001; and 67% vs. 41%, p<0.001, respectively).

Finally, a binary logistic regression analysis was performed to detect hypertrophy. We obtained that age with an odds ratio of 1.06 (95%CI 1.00 – 1.12) (p<0.05) for an increment of 1 year, gender (ref. male) with an odds ratio of 0.30 (95%CI 0.13 – 0.72) (p<0.01), obesity (ref. obese) with 8.28 (95%CI 2.90 – 23.69) (p<0.001), Vp with an odds ratio of 0.90 (95%CI 0.85 – 0.95) (p<0.001) for an increment of 1 cm/s, and sTNF-R1 (above 354 pg/mL) with an odds ratio of 2.59 (95%CI 1.14 – 5.87) (p<0.05) were independent predictors of LVH. All other variables included in the Model (known HT duration, SBP, EF, GFR, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra) failed to reach statistical significance.

DISCUSSION

In this work, we evaluated the relationship of inflammatory markers with LVH in a group of essential hypertensive patients and we also investigated the diagnostic and predictive power of these markers for hypertrophy, as recently it has been made using NT-proBNP levels¹⁷. Ventricular wall stress is the principal factor stimulating brain

natriuretic peptide synthesis and release from cardiomyocytes^{18,19}. Furthermore, this stress also produces an increase in cytokine levels, and the cytokines amplify the signal, because they have a pleiotropic effect²⁰. In addition, elevated cytokine levels are detectable prior to neurohormonal activation in early heart failure²¹.

Furthermore, this is one of the first studies that have addressed the possible relationship between elevated blood pressure and LVH with inflammatory activation in patients with essential HT, using well-established markers of inflammation in cardiology, TNF-alpha receptors, IL-6 and IL-1ra²².

The results of the present study show that the profile of circulating cytokines and cytokine receptors is altered in patients with essential HT. There was a significant increase in the plasma levels of these inflammation markers in hypertensive patients with LVH when compared with non-LVH group. Although the molecular mechanisms by which high blood pressure leads to inflammation are uncertain, some works have reported that abnormalities in the production of cytokines in hypertensive patients reflect monocyte activation induced by endothelial damage as a direct result of mechanical stress produced by an increase in blood pressure¹. Other potential mediators could be the presence of microalbuminuria²³ or metabolic syndrome²⁴. Furthermore, our results are in concordance with previous studies in vitro which have suggested that several cytokines are related to cardiomyocyte hypertrophy²⁵.

Significant correlations were observed between cytokine concentrations with blood pressure and LVMI. Previous studies had already reported results on the relationship between markers of inflammation such as IL-6 and IL-1ra with blood pressure^{3, 4}. Moreover, we also found that the levels of all the inflammatory markers studied were correlated with body mass index and waist circumference.

When we performed a multivariate linear regression analysis, sTNF-R1, known HT duration, body mass index, glomerular filtration rate and diastolic function (Vp) were independent predictors of LVMI. Note the lack of significance with sTNF-R2 in this model, emphasizing the fact that the intracellular domains of these receptors (sTNF-R1 and sTNF-R2) are different, and each receptor activating both distinct and overlapping intracellular signal pathways²⁶. An aspect to consider is that the two groups of hypertensive patients with and without LVH were not matched for age (65±13 vs. 53±11 years old). Nevertheless, the results of the multivariate linear regression analysis were adjusted for these variables; this fact gives validity to our results.

An interesting additional finding is that these inflammatory markers were found to detect LVH. The ROC curve analyses performed suggest that under the designated conditions, all the cytokine tested obtained a significant AUC, sTNF-R1 being the best discriminator between hypertensive patients with and without LVH.

In addition, when a logistic regression analysis was performed to predict hypertrophy, only sTNF-R1 (included in the model as categorical variables according to the cut-off values selected from the ROC curves) was independent predictor. Furthermore, the fact that age and diastolic function (Vp) are predictive factors of LVH agrees with previous studies that show higher prevalence of hypertrophy in older subjects, which to a certain degree is accompanied by diastolic dysfunction²⁷. In addition, obesity is associated with an inflammation state that induces insulin resistance and endothelial dysfunction²⁸.

In summary, more work is necessary to fully understand the role of the cytokines studied in the development and evolution of essential hypertension. Cytokine concentrations could be considered therapeutic targets and could change the prognosis

of hypertensive patients, because the development of LVH in hypertensive patients is associated with higher cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

Study limitations. A common limitation with these kinds of studies is that patients, are receiving conventional therapy for their disease (ethical commitment), and it is known that several kinds of drugs can reduce cytokine levels. In fact, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and beta blockers have been shown to decrease plasma levels of inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines^{29, 30}, although in vivo effect of these medications on the studied cytokines has not yet evaluated. However, this study confirms that a high degree of immune activation persists in hypertensive patients even during standard therapy and this activation can be detected in plasma.

The study of cytokine levels in peripheral venous blood is less accurate than levels obtained in the coronary sinus^{31, 32}. However, our results still show a clear correlation between the parameters studied and the activation of the immune system.

Another potential limitation is that although echocardiography-standardized techniques have been shown to be a more sensitive tool for detecting LVH than electrocardiographic measurements³³, the variability of this technique is higher than the variability using magnetic resonance imaging. However, in the present study a single, blinded, specialized cardiologist performed the echocardiographic analyses used to measure the left ventricular mass to minimize variability. Furthermore, another limitation is that the predictive performance of cytokine concentrations could not be compared to that obtained from conventional ECG, due to insufficient ECG data.

Another consideration is that this work is a cross-sectional study, so it is not designed to evaluate pathophysiological mechanisms (no cause-and-effect inference is possible). However, this work assesses the predictive role and association of different

cytokine levels with left ventricular hypertrophy in a group of patients with essential hypertension.

Finally, another aspect is the lack of standardization of cytokine immunoassays, so the diagnostic accuracy (cut-off values of ROC curves) can depend on patient selection and on cytokine selected, as well as on the analytical performance and the immunoassay chosen.

Conclusions

Plasma cytokine levels were correlated with high blood pressure and left ventricular mass index in hypertensive patients. Plasma sTNF-R1 **was an independent predictor of** left ventricular mass index and left ventricular hypertrophy. These findings support the relationship between the immune system activation and the presence of hypertrophy in patients with essential hypertension.

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FIGURE LEGEND

Figure 1. Prevalence of hypertrophy in hypertensive patients according to the cut-off values selected from the ROC curves.

P value is referred to prevalence of hypertrophy in the group with lower concentrations of cytokines vs the group with higher cytokine levels.

IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-1ra, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist; LVH, left ventricular hypertrophy; sTNF-R1, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1; sTNF-R2, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2.

Table 1. Characteristics of hypertensive patients.

	WITH LVH (N=142)	WITHOUT LVH (N=109)	p VALUE
Age (years)	65±13	53±11	<0.001
Gender (female %)	61	28	<0.001
Known HT duration (months)	115±109	61±66	<0.001
SBP (mmHg)	152±23	145±16	<0.05
DBP (mmHg)	87±12	87±11	0.55
PP (mmHg)	65±20	58±14	<0.01
Heart rate (beats/min)	71±13	71±13	0.68
Waist circumference (cm)	101±10	99±10	0.09
BMI (Kg/m ²)	31±5	28±3	0.001
Diabetes mellitus (%)	18	17	0.87
GFR (mL/min)	85±40	103±30	<0.001
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	0.97±0.30	0.96±0.20	0.44
LDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	132±33	135±32	0.47
HDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	51±13	49±12	0.27
Current smoking (%)	15	20	0.10
Echo-Doppler variables:			
LVEF	59±5	59±5	0.69
E/A	0.82±0.24	0.99±0.23	<0.001
Vp (cm/s)	44±10	54±10	<0.001
ESVI (ml/m ²)	25±7	23±6	<0.01
EDVI (mL/m ²)	60±14	56±13	<0.01

LVMI (g/m ^{2.7})	63±15	39±6	<0.001
IVSDT (mm)	12.5±0.1	11.3±0.09	<0.001
PWDT (mm)	12.1±0.1	11.1±0.08	<0.001
Left atrial size (cm)	3.50±0.39	3.31±0.44	<0.05
RWT	0.54±0.09	0.51±0.08	<0.05

Data are presented as the mean value ± SD or percentage of subjects.

BMI, body mass index; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; E/A, flow velocity in early diastole and during atrial contraction ratio; EDVI, end-diastolic volume index; ESVI, end-systolic volume index; GFR, glomerular filtration rate; HT, hypertension; HDL, high density lipoprotein; IVSDT, interventricular septal diastolic thickness; LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; LVMI, left ventricular mass index; LVH, left ventricular hypertrophy; LDL, low density lipoprotein; PWDT, posterior wall diastolic thickness; PP, pulse pressure; RWT, relative wall thickness; SBP, systolic blood pressure; Vp, mitral flow propagation velocity.

Table 2. Cytokine and cytokine receptors levels in the study population.

	PATIENTS			p*
	ALL (N=251)	WITHOUT LVH (N=109)	WITH LVH (N=142)	
sTNFR1 (pg/mL)	382 (291-541)	317 (260-421)	453 (322-645)	<0.001
sTNF-R2 (pg/mL)	852 (585-1214)	763 (491-1072)	1086 (624-1358)	<0.001
IL-6 (pg/mL)	2.34 (1.49-3.37)	1.86 (1.27-2.66)	2.83 (1.85-3.59)	<0.001
IL-1ra (pg/mL)	195(135-263)	164 (115-230)	223 (165-299)	<0.001

Data are presented as the median value and interquartile range.

* Hypertrophic vs. non-hypertrophic

IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-1ra, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist; LVH, left ventricular hypertrophy; sTNF-R1, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1; sTNF-R2, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2.

Table 3. Spearman's correlation coefficient (r) between inflammation markers and different variables in hypertensive patients (n=251).

Variable	sTNF-R1 (pg/mL)	sTNF-R2 (pg/mL)	IL-6 (pg/mL)	IL-1ra (pg/mL)
Age (years)	0.55 ‡	0.47 ‡	0.38 ‡	0.20 ‡
SBP (mm Hg)	0.18 †	0.19 †	0.18 †	0.04
PP (mm Hg)	0.27 ‡	0.25 ‡	0.22 ‡	0.13 *
GFR (mL/min)	-0.47 ‡	-0.39 ‡	-0.22 ‡	0.07
LVMI (g/m ^{2.7})	0.38 ‡	0.26 ‡	0.32 ‡	0.24 ‡
BMI (kg/m ²)	0.19 †	0.15 *	0.27 ‡	0.33 ‡
Waist circumference (cm)	0.20 ‡	0.13 *	0.24 ‡	0.24 ‡
EF (%)	-0.15 *	-0.18 †	-0.19 †	-0.02
Vp (cm/s)	-0.39 ‡	-0.26 ‡	-0.24 ‡	-0.09

* p<0.05, † p<0.01, ‡ p<0.001

BMI, body mass index; EF, ejection fraction; GFR, glomerular filtration rate; IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-1ra, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist; LVMI, left ventricular mass index; PP, pulse pressure; sTNF-R1, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1; sTNF-R2, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2; SBP, systolic blood pressure; Vp, mitral flow propagation velocity.

Table 4. Multivariate linear regression results to detect independent factors on left ventricular mass index in hypertensive patients (n=251).

	Unstandardized			
	Coefficients			
	B	SE	95% CI	P value
Model 1				
Age	0.438	0.082	0.227-0.599	<0.001
Gender	-4.517	1.930	-8.319- -0.716	<0.05
log sTNF-R1	0.016	0.005	0.007-0.025	<0.01
log sTNF-R2	-0.001	0.002	(-0.006)-0.003	0.59
log IL-6	-0.159	0.424	(-0.995)-0.677	0.71
log IL-1ra	0.000	0.006	(-0.012)-0.012	0.97
Model 2				
Age	0.039	0.155	(-0.267)-0.345	0.80
Gender	-2.136	2.301	(-6.692) -2.421	0.36
Known HT duration	0.029	0.012	0.005-0.052	<0.05
SBP	0.046	0.052	(-0.057)-0.150	0.38
BMI	1.685	0.340	1.013-2.358	<0.001
EF	0.023	0.197	(-0.367) -0.412	0.91
Vp	-0.470	0.114	(-0.696)- (-0.244)	<0.001
GFR	-0.137	0.068	(-0.272)- (-0.003)	<0.05
ARA II	-0.285	2.773	(-5.776)-5.207	0.92
ECA inhibitors	-1.023	2.911	(-6.786)-4.741	0.73
Diuretics	-3.713	2.170	(-8.009)-0.584	0.90
Beta blockers	2.689	2.560	(-2.379)-7.757	0.30

log sTNF-R1	0.015	0.006	0.003-0.027	<0.01
log sTNF-R2	-0.001	0.002	(-0.006)-0.003	0.56
log IL-6	-0.384	0.455	(-1.285)-0.517	0.40
log IL-1ra	-0.007	0.007	(-0.020)-0.006	0.27

Model 1 of regression analysis was associated with an $r^2=0.30$ ($p<0.001$) and Model 2 was associated with an $r^2=0.60$ ($p<0.001$).

ARA II, antagonists receptors of angiotensin type II; BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence interval; ECA, enzyme converting angiotensin; EF, ejection fraction; GFR, glomerular filtration rate; HT, hypertension; IL-6, log transformed interleukin-6 levels; IL-1ra, log transformed interleukin-1 receptor antagonist levels; **SE, standard error**; sTNF-R1, log transformed soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1 levels; sTNF-R2, log transformed soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2 levels; SBP, systolic blood pressure; Vp, mitral flow propagation velocity.

Table 5. ROC-AUCs for plasma sTNF-R1, sTNF-R2, IL-6 and IL-1ra for predicting left ventricular hypertrophy with sensitivities, specificities, and predictive values.

Variable	Cut-off value	AUC	p Value	95% CI	SS	SP	PPV	NPV
sTNF-R1 (pg/mL)	354	0.71	<0.001	0.65-0.78	72	60	71	62
sTNF-R2 (pg/mL)	700	0.63	<0.001	0.57-0.70	70	48	63	55
IL-6 (pg/mL)	2.02	0.66	<0.001	0.59-0.73	70	56	67	58
IL-1ra (pg/mL)	175	0.65	<0.001	0.58-0.72	70	56	67	59

CI, confidence interval; IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-1ra, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist; NPV, negative predictive value; PPV, positive predictive value; ROC-AUC, receiver-operating characteristic area under the curve; SP, specificity; SS, sensitivity; sTNF-R1, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 1; sTNF-R2, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor 2.

FIGURE 1

